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Research Article

**DIAGNOSTIC ACCURACY OF MAGNETIC RESONANCE
IMAGING FOR DETECTION OF MEDIAL MENISCAL
TEARS TAKING ARTHROSCOPY AS GOLD STANDARD**¹Muhammad Usman Iqbal, ²Muhammad Zakriya, ³Fatima¹Muhammad Iqbal, RHC Khutri Banglow Yazman bwp. Dr.Usman.jutt@gmail.com.²Abdul Waheed, BHU Hassu balail Teh AP Sial District Jhang
muhammadzakriya980@gmail.com³D/o Ghulam Muhammad Shoukat, Tehsil Mailsi district vehari, House job. BVH
Bahawalpur, dr.fatima78692@gmail.com.**Article Received:** May 2020**Accepted:** June 2020**Published:** July 2020**Abstract:****Background:** The purpose of the study is to analyze and compare the results of MRI diagnostic accuracy with the arthroscopy taking as a gold standard in meniscal injuries.**Methodology:** The patients with knee injuries who were referred to Radiology Department of Lahore General Hospital for MRI after clinical examinations were included in the study with their consent. Sample size was taken 200 and those patients after MRI scan were referred for arthroscopy.**Results:** The sensitivity, specificity and diagnostic accuracy of MRI was calculated after the results of arthroscopy which was set as a gold standard which was 67%, 87% and 85% respectively. RI is a good screening option to avoid arthroscopy in knee injury patients.**Conclusion:** To assess the meniscal and ligamentous injuries the MRI is an excellent noninvasive option. It can be used for the screening of patients for arthroscopy which was set as a gold standard in meniscal tears and knee injury.**Keywords:** Arthroscopy, Meniscal tears, MRI, ACL, knee injury, PCL**Corresponding author:****Muhammad Usman Iqbal,**

RHC Khutri Banglow Yazman bwp.

Dr.Usman.jutt@gmail.com

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

Knee joint injuries are common due to sports activities and traffic accidents on roads. Meniscus and ligament injuries hinder the routine activities due to unstable knee joint. Therefore, it is important to timely manage and diagnose the knee injuries in order to carry the routine activities without any hassle. Knee injuries can be managed either conservatively or by the surgeries. Meniscal tear common risk factors are twisting, stress and degenerative tears in old age. Tears can be classified as vertical, horizontal, anterior, degenerative, radial, traumatic, lateral, bucket handle and like parrot beak. Knee joint is considered the most complex joint and largest in human body. Stability in knee joint is provided by ligaments, bone structure, menisci and capsules and tendons and muscles provide stabilization.³ Menisci structure is made of fibro cartilage which is 2/3 of tibial plateau joint exterior. The meniscus work is to share load and help in shock absorption, provide feed to cartilage with the help of joint fluid. Also the joint stability and joint contact surface is the function of meniscus. Due to their functions and exposures the menisci structure is injured on frequent basis. Knee muscle injuries are common among males due to their external exposure and involvement in sports. The rate of meniscus injury is 60 per one lac population. Intra articular knee injury is observed common which involves meniscal lesions. Therefore the orthopedists routine surgeries involve the meniscectomy which may be partial or complete depending upon the condition/results (MRI diagnosis) of the patients. The patients who appeared with knee injury in the Hospitals were observed meniscal tears among 68 % of the patients. MRI (magnetic resonance imaging) is good option and can also be considered gold standard in term of diagnostic accuracy in identifying the meniscal tears and other abnormalities. The diagnosis of meniscal tears is also expertise based and sometime the results are not as accurate as considered. In 47 % of the cases the results were misleading. MRI is also expensive and is not readily available to general public in remote areas.⁶ Meniscal tears MRI diagnosis accuracy was observed 75% by the study of Rose et al. according to him MRI is expensive and extra burden on the patient who have clear symptoms of meniscal injury.⁷ Another study conducted by Khandelwal et al conclude that the sensitivity of MRI is 95.6%, specificity was 94.8% and diagnostic accuracy of MRI is 95.2% which is

highly reliable diagnostic option for patients who can afford it. The purpose of the study is to confirm the diagnostic accuracy of MRI in the identification of medical meniscal tears and the gold standard set was the arthroscopy. MRI can help in the avoidance of the useless arthroscopies and can also assist the surgeons to reduce the surgery time by identifying the exact location of tear. Due to harmless imaging technique the MRI helps to identify all the abnormalities in knee with help of planes. Studies of the MRI diagnostic accuracy in meniscal knee injuries are not common. Therefore, the present study will augment the performance and accuracy of MRI in the meniscal injury in order to avoid the unnecessary arthroscopies in the patients. The MRI diagnosis will help to enhance the clinical practices and surgeons for meniscal injuries surgery.

METHODOLOGY:

The study was conducted in Lahore General Hospital Radiology Department from period of Jan 2019 to August 2019. Sample sizes selected was 200 patients who have knee injury due to trauma or other reasons

Inclusion criteria: Patients from 11 to 60 years were included in the study with complain of knee injury and were referred to MRI for diagnosis and they were also suggested and went for arthroscopy as therapeutic option.

Exclusion criteria: Patients sensitive to MRI, pregnant ladies, cardiac pace maker and any implant in the body were excluded from the study.

Demographic characteristics (gender, age, economic position, name, injury duration) of the patients were also noted who were willingly participating in the study. The MRI was performed by senior radiologist with 1.5 tesla and 3 tesla MRI machines. The patients were considered positive and negative according to the results of MRI and later arthroscopy by surgeon under spinal anesthesia. Patients after arthroscopy will be confirmed for medical meniscal tears as positive or negative.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS:

Sensitivity, specificity, negative predictive value and positive predictive values were calculated. The table 1 is about the gender participation and their age group distribution according to the total participants. The side involved in knee injury is explained.

Table 1

Age	Cases #	Percentage
10-19	18	0.09%
20-29	90	0.45%
30-39	68	0.34%
40-49	20	0.1%
50-60	4	0.02%
Gender	Case #	Percentage
Male	156	0.78%
Female	44	0.22%
Position	Cases	Percentage
Right	112	0.56%
Left	88	0.44%

The above table is about the age and sex of the participants and also the position of their knee. Male participants were 156 and female were 44. The age group distribution of the patients is also described. Majority of the patients were young male which shows the tendency of the male population who were at higher risk due to road accidents while driving motor bikes and also due to sports activities. Female population was less in number and less at risk of getting injured due to their minimum external exposure. Fritz et al study also confirms that the male are at higher risk of getting knee injuries due sports and accidents.

From the table it is also clear that the right side of knee cases were 112(56%) and left side was 88(44%)

Table 2

Injury structure	Physical examination	Diagnostic MRI	Arthroscopy	Sensitivity	Specificity	PPV	NPV
ACL	135	140	140	93%	82%	82%	92%
PCL	2	5	5	100%	100%	100%	100%
Medical Meniscus	55	101	60	82%	65%	55%	89%
Lateral Meniscus	20	40	30	67%	87%	52%	93%

The table 2 describes the structure of injury . The MRI results confirmed the 101 cases of medical meniscus injury and after the arthroscopy the medical meniscus was confirmed in 60 patients. This shows the sensitivity of MRI in the medical meniscus injury as 82% and specificity was 65%. Study conducted by Elvenes et al showed the results about the meniscal tears were as sensitivity, specificity 77%.PPV (Positive predictive value) 71% and NPV (negative predictive value) as 100%.

In our study the sensitivity was 67%, specificity was 87%, positive predictive value was 55% and negative predictive value was 89%.

In the study the MRI identified 40 cases of lateral menisci injuries and after the arthroscopy the lateral menisci injuries were confirmed in 30 cases. The sensitivity of MRI in lateral meniscus cases were 67% and specificity was 87%. It is considered a good diagnosis in identifying the lateral meniscal injuries with the help of MRI. Positive predictive value was 52% and negative predictive value was 93%. It means the specificity of MRI results is higher as compared to the sensitivity and also the

negative predictive value was higher as compared to positive predictive value. When combined together the overall diagnostic accuracy of MRI in identifying the lateral and medical meniscus injuries were 85%.Due to higher specificity and negative predictive value the MRI results help to exclude the patients from unnecessary arthroscopies .From the table indicating structure of injuries the anterior cruciate ligament (ACL) injury was higher in number consisting of 140 patients and only false positive cases were 5 which were observed during the clinical examination only. The sensitivity of the MRI in ACL cases after the results of arthroscopy was 93% and the specificity was 82%. Positive predictive value of MRI was 92% and negative predictive value was 82%. From the total cases, the PCL (posterior cruciate ligament) were found in 5 cases in the MRI results and in the arthroscopy results confirmed five posterior cruciate ligament injured patients. Hence the correlation identified between the results of MRI and arthroscopy was excellent it identified 100% correlation and hence the specificity, sensitivity, PPV and NPV was 100%.

CONCLUSION:

Knee injuries are common in road accidents and in sports activities. For proper management of knee injury and their output it is important to evaluate and plan their treatment accordingly. Otherwise it will hinder the movement and stability of the patients. MRI is considered a gold diagnostic option for treatment plan of knee injury either conventionally or surgically. MRI helps to identify the meniscus tears and injury to cruciate ligaments. In all cases of knee injury arthroscopy remained the gold standard for treatment after diagnosis of the problem. MRI is used to support the clinical findings and examination. The diagnosis with MRI helps in arthroscopies of the patients. From the study it was clear that the negative predictive value and specificity was high which help in excluding the patients who do not require arthroscopy.

REFERENCES:

1. Francavilla ML, Restrepo R, Zamora KW, Sarode V, Swirsky SM, Mintz D. Meniscal pathology in children: differences and similarities with the adult meniscus. *Pediatric radiology* 2014 Aug;44(8):910-25; quiz 07-9.
2. Rao AJ, Erickson BJ, Cvetanovich GL, Yanke AB, Bach BR, Jr., Cole BJ. The Meniscus-Deficient Knee: Biomechanics, Evaluation, and Treatment Options. *Orthop J Sports Med* 2015;3(10):2325967115611386-3. Kılıç B. Six year follow-up after arthroscopic meniscectomy. *Advances in Environmental Biology* 2015;9(2):50-3.
3. Sari A, Günaydin B, Dinçel YM. Meniscus Tears and Review of the Literature. Online: IntechOpen; 2018.
4. Ridley TJ, McCarthy MA, Bollier MJ, Wolf BR, Amendola A. Age Differences in the Prevalence of Isolated Medial and Lateral Meniscal Tears in Surgically Treated Patients. *Iowa Orthop J* 2017;37:91-4.
5. Cook JL, Cook CR, Stannard JP, Vaughn G, Wilson N, Roller BL, et al. MRI versus ultrasonography to assess meniscal abnormalities in acute knees. *The journal of knee surgery* 2014 Aug;27(4):319-24.
6. Rose NE, Gold SM. A comparison of accuracy between clinical examination and magnetic resonance imaging in the diagnosis of meniscal and anterior cruciate ligament tears. *Arthroscopy : the journal of arthroscopic & related surgery : official publication of the Arthroscopy Association of North America and the International Arthroscopy Association* 1996 Aug;12(4):398-405.
7. Khandelwal K, Chaturvedi V, Mishra V, Khandelwal G. Diagnostic accuracy of MRI knee in reference to arthroscopy in meniscal and anterior cruciate ligament injuries. *The Egyptian Journal of Radiology and Nuclear Medicine* 2018;49(1):138-45.
8. Gray SD, Kalpan PA, Dussault RG. Imaging of Knee: current status. *OCNA* 1997; 28(4): 643-658.
9. Kaplan PA, Walker CW, Kilcoyne RF, Brown DE, Tusek D, Dussault RG. Occult fractures patterns of the knee associated with ACL tears. Assessment with MR imaging. *Radiology* 1992; 183: 835-838.
10. Boden SD, Labropoulos PA, Vailas JC: MR Scanning of the acutely injured knee: sensitive, but is cost effective? *Arthroscopy* 1990; 6: 306-308.
11. CH Bennet & Chebli, "Knee arthroscopy"
12. Fritz, J., Janssen, P., Gaissmaier, C., Schewe, B., & Weise, K. (2008). Articular cartilage defects in the knee—Basics, therapies and results. *Injury*, 39(1), 50-57.
13. Elvenes J, Jerome CP, Reikeras O, Johansen O. MRI as a screening procedure to avoid Arthroscopy for meniscal tears. *Arch Orthop Trauma Surg* 2000; 120(1- 2): 14-16.
14. John B McGinty, Richard B. Caspar!, Robert W. Jackson, Eds. *Operative Arthroscopy*, 2nd edition, Lippincott-Raven 1997; 1-7, 175-189.
15. Mackenzie R, Dixon AK, Keene GS, et al: Magnetic resonance imaging of the knee; assessment of the effectiveness, *clin Radiol* 51:245-50,1996